

A Constitutive Model for DYNEEMA UD composites

L Iannucci¹, D J Pope², M Dalzell²

¹Imperial College, Department of Aeronautics
London, SW7 2AZ

liannucci@imperial.ac.uk

²Dstl, Porton Down, Salisbury, Wiltshire
SP4 0JQ

SUMMARY

The mechanical properties and overall material response of Dyneema UD composites has been investigated. The relevant tests indicate that Dyneema UD has very low compressive and shear strengths. A new constitutive model has been developed and implemented into the ls-dyna Finite Element code and used to simulate a high velocity impacts.

Keywords: Dyneema, Finite Element, Composite Impact, Failure, High Performance Fibres

INTRODUCTION

In the last 15 years a large number of new high performance polymer fibres with aligned carbon chains have been developed, which include Aramid fibres (Kevlar, Twaron, Technora), polyethylene fibres (Dyneema, Spectre), polypropylene fibres (Curv, Tegrin) and PBO (Zylon). The main market for these low density fibres with high tenacity is lightweight body armour, such as vests and helmets. However, they also have applications in improving crashworthiness and fragmentation resistance from a wide range of possible threats.

Impact energy is dissipated by wave propagation along the fibres; the controlling materials properties are the tensile wave velocity in the fibres and the specific energy absorbed at failure. These properties make high performance polyethylene (HPPE) and polypropylene (HPPP) attractive in impact protection systems and containment devices. To fully exploit the potential performance of these materials a robust material model is required. This paper describes an implemented into the LS-DYNA Finite Element (FE) code of a plane stress material model; a more detailed 3D version of the model described has also been developed for application in which a 3D stress field is important and the use of an Equation Of State (EOS) is a requirement. The first part of this paper highlights a number of on-going material tests on a Dyneema UD composite (a 0/90 laminated composite, rather than a woven architecture).

LABORATORY TESTS

A series of laboratory tests were performed on Dyneema UD composites. The composite has been found to have a low shear and compressive strength, while the tensile strength and strain to failure are excellent for a polymer. The tensile behaviour is shown in Figure 1. The vertical error bar illustrated in Figure 1 left relates to the variability in testing three specimens. Figure 1 right uses the same specimen, but with two unloading cycles. The unloading cycle indicates that unloading to be almost linear.

The residual strain could hence be related to the opening of matrix cracks or splitting in the 90 layer, or plasticity in the fibres or matrix.

Figure 1 Tensile stress strain curve for Dyneema UD composite

For the modelling, it is assumed that the initial nonlinear region of the stress-strain is associated with matrix damage, unloading is always along an elastic damaged modulus. Figure 2 shows the final damage specimen. It is not directly apparent in Figure 2, but all laminae layers were delaminated within the specimen. The specimen did not use tabs, but hydraulic grips due to severe difficulties in holding the specimen until failure. Some researchers melt the ends and then grip, this approach could well damage the composite. It is not clear whether these delaminations started at the free edge of the specimen, or at the grips, but was observed to start once matrix damage commenced. Hence they may have initiated from the stress concentration at the matrix cracking or splitting sites. This requires further investigation.

Figure 2 Tension Dyneema UD crossply specimen

Figure 3 Failed surface of tensile specimen (potential fibrillation and drawing of fibres).

Figure 3 shows the fractured surfaces; note the potential fibrillation and drawing of fibres. This is modelled with a further damage variable which simulates the strain softening behaviour and is associated with damage in the fibres. A further series of tests were performed in a standard tension-shear configuration to investigate the behaviour in pure in-plane shear.

Figure 4 Tension-shear stress strain curve for Dyneema UD composite

Figure 4 left illustrates the non-linear shear with the error bars associated with the scatter in three tests. The Figure on the right illustrates the cyclic unloading behaviour. A highly non-linear behaviour during unloading is observed this is potentially due to matrix damage and the friction between the failed surfaces. This is clearly evident in Figure 5. As the fibres re-orient towards the end of the loading regime the stiffening response of the specimen is potentially associated with fibre reorientation.

Figure 5 Failed tension-shear specimen

Failure appeared to initiate from the grips, generating a series of fracture surface along the specimen in a cone shaped pattern.

A final series of static tests were performed to investigate the compressive behaviour. These are shown in Figure 6 with the unloading curves in Figure 6 right. The compressive behaviour is dominated by microscale kinking of the fibres. The initial peak is probably associated with their formation, followed by a plateau regime in which the kinks slide as more or less constant stress. Thus in the following modelling section it is proposed to model the behaviour as an elastic-plastic material along fibre directions only.

A series of impacts were also performed on Dyneema UD crossply laminates to determine the ballistic limit and to use the results to validate the proposed constitutive model, Table 1. The ballistic limit can be defined as the lowest initial projectile velocity that will result in complete penetration of the structure. It can be found by conducting a

series of test shots against samples of the material at increasing initial projectile impact velocity.

Figure 6 Compressive stress strain curve for Dyneema UD composite

By plotting these velocities against the residual velocity measured (the velocity of the projectile after it has passed through the structure) it is possible to determine the lowest velocity that results in penetration. Figure 7 and 8 illustrates the panel at the ballistic limit. The excessive displacements and drawing of the laminate is clearly evident. The deformation pattern would indicate a very low shear and compressive strengths. This has been confirmed from the static test conducted.

Table 1 Summary of experimental results from high velocity gas gun testing

Testing Regimes	Projectile Used	Mass of Projectile (g)	Velocity Range (m/s)	Areal Density (Kg/m ²)	Ballistic Limit (m/s)
0.8 mm Dyneema panels	6mm Mild Steel ball	0.8677	305-388	5.7	305

Figure 7 Ballistic impact on Dyneema UD crossply laminate near the ballistic limit

Figure 8 Ballistic impact on Dyneema UD crossply laminate near the ballistic limit

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The present paper describes the implementation into the explicit FE code LS-DYNA of a damage mechanics based failure model and is based on the extension of existing plane stress models [1, 2]. The formulation is concerned primarily with in-plane failure of thin high performance laminated UD composites. In this particular case a thin Dyneema UD composite. In the present formulation four damage variables are introduced to model the observed matrix and fibre damage. Compression failure is model with two plastic strain measures. The shear response follows a non-linear behaviour. Unloading always follows the elastic unloading slope before damage commences, but unloads with the damaged modulus when damage has initiated. Again, this is a convenient assumption, which captures the non-linear elastic and permanent strain behaviour. The fracture process is implicit within the stress-strain relationship for the composite material. The damage mechanics methodology *must* hence be based on a Unit Cell (UC), unlike classical fracture mechanics.

Stiffness Degradation

Each Unit Cell (UC) consists of a 0 and 90 UD Dyneema ply; basically a cross-ply. Using a simple mosaic modelling approach it is possible to derive the cross-ply stiffness in each of local direction within the unit cell, i.e. 0 and 90 layer. Hence for the local x-direction it takes the following form:

$$E_{xx} = f_x(E_f, E_m, d_{mx}, d_{fx}, V_f, V_m) \quad (1)$$

and the local y-direction;

$$E_{yy} = f_y(E_f, E_m, d_{my}, d_{fy}, V_f, V_m). \quad (2)$$

In the above equation the individual matrix and fibre modulus can be non-linear, a function of strain-rate, temperature, or include a plastic strain component.

Understanding the exact behavior of both the matrix and fibre is currently on-going. The procedure does not take into account any fibre crimp. The first layer can be defined as:

$$E_{xx_1} = 0.5(V_f E_f + V_m E_m)(1 - c_{12}d_{fx}) \quad (3)$$

and the second layer,

$$E_{xx_2} = 0.5 \left(\frac{E_f E_m (1 - c_{11}d_{mx})}{V_m E_f + V_f E_m (1 - c_{11}d_{mx})} \right) \quad (4)$$

The above two expressions refer to the theory of mixtures in a parallel model and series model respectively. Where

d_{mx} = Matrix cracking in x-direction (local)

d_{fx} = Fibre fracture in x-direction (local)

E_m = Young's Modulus of matrix

E_f = Young's Modulus of fibre

V_m = Volume fracture of matrix

V_f = Volume fracture of fibre

c_{11} = a constant usually set to 0.999

c_{12} = a constant usually set to 0.999

The total Young's modulus in the local x-direction can be given by combining Equations (3) and (4),

$$E_{xx} = E_{xx_1} + E_{xx_2} \quad (5)$$

The local y-direction can be treated in a similar manner yielding;

$$E_{yy} = 0.5(V_f E_f + V_m E_m)(1 - c_{25}d_{fy}) + 0.5\left(\frac{E_f E_m(1 - c_{24}d_{my})}{V_m E_f + V_f E_m(1 - c_{24}d_{my})}\right) \quad (6)$$

No coupling terms have been included between the local x- and local y-directions for the Young's modulus terms. The additional definitions are defined as;

d_{my} = matrix cracking in y-direction (local)

d_{fy} = fibre fracture in y-direction (local).

A simple non-linear shear stress-strain behaviour is assumed for the in-plane shear response. The shear stress-strain response is defined as:

$$\tau = A\gamma^3 + B\gamma^2 + C\gamma + D, \quad (7)$$

with $D=0.0$, $C=109.61$, $B=-580.424$, $A=1120.77$ in units of MPa for the curve shown in Figure 4. The instantaneous shear modulus can be trivially derived using the above equation.

Matrix Cracks Evolution

Matrix cracks damage evolution in the local x-direction is defined as;

$$\dot{d}_{mx} = (a_{10} + a_{11}d_{mx})\left[\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_{Thres,m,x}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \quad (8)$$

and in the local y-direction;

$$\dot{d}_{my} = \left(a_{40} + a_{44} d_{my} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_{Thres,m,y}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \quad (9)$$

where

- $\sigma_{Thres,m,x}$ = threshold for matrix cracks in local x-direction of the UC
- $\sigma_{Thres,m,y}$ = threshold for matrix cracks in local y-direction of the UC
- d_{mx} = local x matrix cracks damage (can range between 0 and 1)
- d_{my} = local y matrix cracks damage (can range between 0 and 1)
- \dot{d}_{mx} = matrix cracks damage-rate in local x-direction ($\dot{d}_{mx} > 0$)
- \dot{d}_{my} = matrix cracks damage-rate in local y-direction ($\dot{d}_{my} > 0$)
- $\sigma_x \sigma_y$ = local x-stresses
- a_{ij} = are positive constants

Equations (8) and (9) represent a damage rate for matrix crack evolution in the composite. The constants a_{10} and a_{40} control the nucleation period for matrix cracks, while constants a_{11} and a_{44} control the growth period of matrix cracks. The same stress threshold is used for both nucleation and growth. This threshold stress for matrix cracks also reduces as damage grows. The relationship for the local x-direction is defined by:

$$\sigma_{Thres,m,x} = \sigma_{Thres,m,x,0} \left(\frac{E_{xx}}{E_{xx_0}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where

- $\sigma_{Thres,m,x}$ = Threshold for start of matrix cracks
- E_{xx} = Current Young's Modulus of composite
- E_{xx_0} = Initial Young's Modulus of composite

The local y-direction is defined by:

$$\sigma_{Thres,m,y} = \sigma_{Thres,m,y,0} \left(\frac{E_{yy}}{E_{yy_0}} \right) \quad (11)$$

where

- $\sigma_{Thres,m,y}$ = Initial threshold for start of matrix cracks
- E_{yy} = Current Young's Modulus of composite
- E_{yy_0} = Initial Young's Modulus of composite

A damage rate limit is used for each damage evolution rate. This is tentatively related to the Rayleigh wave speed in the matrix, i.e. damage cannot grow faster than the physical wave speed in the material.

The damage mechanics approach to modelling matrix cracks permits the degradation of the material elastic constants (matrix only), using the theory of mixtures. Furthermore to prevent non-physical energy growth and to maintain positive definiteness in the material stiffness matrix, a series of inequalities relating to degradation must be satisfied [1, 2].

Fibre Fracture Evolution

Fibre fracture damage evolution in the local x-direction is defined by:

$$\dot{d}_{fx} = \left(a_{21}d_{mx} + a_{22}d_{fx} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_{Thres,f,x}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \quad (12)$$

The above equation assumes nucleation has already occurred via the formation of matrix cracks in the local fabric x-direction. Hence fibre fracture cannot occur unless d_{mx} is greater than zero. Fibre fracture damage evolution in the local y-direction is defined by:

$$\dot{d}_{fy} = \left(a_{54}d_{my} + a_{55}d_{fy} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_{Thres,f,y}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \quad (13)$$

where

- $\sigma_{Thres,f,x}$ = Threshold for fibre fracture in local x-direction of the UC
- $\sigma_{Thres,f,y}$ = Threshold for fibre fracture in local y-direction of the UC
- d_{fx} = Local x matrix cracks damage (can range between 0 and 1)
- d_{fy} = Local y matrix cracks damage (can range between 0 and 1)
- \dot{d}_{fx} = Matrix cracks damage-rate in local x-direction ($\dot{d}_{fx} > 0$)
- \dot{d}_{fy} = Matrix cracks damage-rate in local y-direction ($\dot{d}_{fy} > 0$)
- σ_x, σ_y = Local stresses
- a_{ij} = Are positive constants

Figure 9 Model Stress-fibre damage-strain behaviour with damage d_2 (fibre fracture damage) associated with fibre failure in the 0 degree ply within the UC.

Equations (12) and (13) represent a damage rate for fibre evolution in the composite. The constants a_{ij} control the growth of damage. The threshold for the nucleation of damage in the composite is only governed by Equations (12) and (13), i.e. the nucleation period is assumed to be related directly to the formation matrix cracks.

The threshold stress for fibre fracture also reduces as damage grows. The relationship for the local x-direction is given by similar equations to (10) and (11). The approach adopted in the present composite damage model provides a strain hardening and strain softening relationship, Figure 9, which allows damage to develop gradually.

As damage can gradually develop in an element, the energy dissipated may be greater than the elastic energy of one element. As a damage lag approach is adopted in equation 12 and 13 the strain-rate sensitivity of the material is implicitly included. This information was not available, but approximate enhancement was based on reference in the open literature [3, 4].

High velocity impact model

The UC represent the behaviour of a cross ply. Hence its implementation into a shell element required each integration point to be associated with the UC. For example, if 100 0/90 cross ply are used in the laminate, then 100 integration point should be used to model the macroscale behaviour from the UC mesoscale model. In the present example the experimental results presented in Table 1 are simulated. The projectile is model with an elastic plastic material model and the Dyneema specimen modelled with the new material model. The tests described in the earlier sections were used to derive the material model constants using an inverse approach, or simple curve fitting to the measured data. The predicted deformed pattern exhibits the key feature, such as the excessive drawing of the material and the very large displacement prior to perforation, Figure 10, element deletion occurs when both the 0 and 90 laminae within the UC has failed. Clearly modelling the tensile, compressive and shear behaviour was key in simulating the correct behaviour.

Figure 10 Simulation of high velocity impact before impact and after impact using the new high performance fibre material model.

CONCLUSIONS

Clearly the strain to failure is high for Dyneema, compared with Carbon and Glass composites, and it is essential in armour applications to fully realise the tensile strength. The model approach has been shown to model the global behaviour in great detail. The modelling approach can be used to design the global response of panels, by varying material properties and lamination angles. However, for a detailed 3D behaviour an EoS must be used and element erosion included. In this type of formulation the orthotropic nature of the material is important as the wave speeds can be different depending on the direction within the composite. Furthermore, the material model must include an appropriate orthotropic hydrodynamic formulation, [5].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The material and support from the Dstl SAMPLE programme gratefully acknowledged, and the careful experimental tests performed by Alex Cervero Orfila and Joseph Meggyesi

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